

Design, Modelling and Simulation of Quasi-Resonant Flyback Converter with Power Factor Correction

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ABSTRACT

A quasi-resonant flyback converter (QR-FBC) offers an efficient and cost-effective solution for isolated power supplies by minimizing switching losses and component voltage stress. This paper presents the design of a 100 kHz single-switch QR-FBC with an input voltage of 85–330 VAC and an output of 12V, 60W. The design uses valley switching (VS) for switch turn-on, zero-current switching (ZCS) for switch turn off and zero-current switching (ZCS) for diode turn-off, and resonant energy recycling to enhance efficiency. The LM5023 quasi-resonant PWM controller ensures critical conduction mode, peak-current mode control, skip-cycle mode for low-standby power, and hiccup mode for overload protection. A custom flyback transformer is designed to prevent saturation, while the IPA80R600P7 super junction MOSFET selected for its low $R_{DS(on)}$, supports high-frequency operation. A snubber circuit maintains voltage stress within limits at fixed frequency operation. With an assumed 85% efficiency and 0.9 power factor, this proposed design achieves high performance with fewer components, making it ideal for AC-DC adapters, consumer electronics, and auxiliary power supplies.

KEYWORDS- *Quasi-Resonant Flyback Converter, Zero- Current Switching, AC DC Converter, Valley Switching, Soft Switching, Overload Protection.*

1. INTRODUCTION

Flyback converter topology is widely accepted because of its compact and high efficiency. Where the isolation is very important in power supply there are different topologies are considered, they are –

Forward converters, in forward flyback converters we use another auxiliary winding that resets the transformer magnetizing current. It reduces the current ripple and power loss. It has high switching stress due to the leakage inductance of the transformer. Soft switching is introduced to reduce the voltage spikes of the switch and can be turned off at zero voltage conditions as previously shown (Khalilian and Adib, 2015). Soft switching is done by adding an auxiliary circuit. This circuit absorbs the energy from the leakage inductance and returns it back to the inductor. This gives excellent efficiency but voltage stresses on the component are more and using another inductor circuit increases the overall cost of the product. Also using RCD snubber circuit makes it less efficient.

Resonant converters, LLC resonance full-bridge DC-DC converter under voltage control mode have been widely used in medium power applications because of the high efficiency of its magnetic core and power density. It uses ZCS and ZVS so that the loss is minimum and efficiency is high. However, in voltage control mode it shows nonlinear behaviour like bifurcations and chaos as shown by Xie et al. (2014). Also, its control loop design is complex because the resonant tank introduces frequency-dependent dynamics, which interact with the feedback loop. This topology gives excellent performance characteristics in high frequency but the cost of the component goes higher for high frequency.

Quasi Resonant flyback converter, is a type of a flyback converter which introduces some concepts of resonant converters to minimize its switching losses and stresses upon the component used. It has the advantages of LLC resonant converter and also the forward converter. This topology incorporates resonance between the resonant inductor (Leakage inductance of transformer) and the resonant capacitor (switch drain to source capacitor). By using these resonance oscillations valley

switching turn-on of the switch and zero current switching turn-off of the diode and MOSFET is achieved. This feature also recycles back the transformer leakage energy. The prior work includes increasing the switching frequency and also adaptive switching frequency for improved efficiency. Different digital control strategies are incorporated such as bidirectional quasi resonant converter and pulse frequency modulation. Integration with wide bandgap semiconductors and power factor correction integration makes the design more efficient and robust. The topology discussed in this paper uses fixed frequency PWM controlled flyback transformer and uses a capacitor in parallel with diode which minimizes loss and interference. Thus, the design is designed to deliver higher efficiency than the two conventional topologies while maintaining excellent performance at a lower cost.

2. QUASI RESONANCE FLYBACK CONVERTER CIRCUIT AND OPERATION

In this paper, a single-switch quasi-resonant flyback converter is proposed with a fixed switching frequency of 100 kHz and a 12V, 60W output prototype. The converter operates with an input voltage range of 85–330 VAC. The simplified outlay of the power circuit is presented in Figure 1. In this paper, the resonance between switch Drain capacitor (C_{oss}) and magnetizing inductance of flyback transformer (L_m) is used to employ turn-on of the switch (Valley switching) also by using a resonant inductor (transformer leakage inductance) and resonant capacitor in parallel with the diode to achieve high efficiency and employ the ZCS turn-off of the diode by recycling back the transformer leakage energy. In the following sections, the detailed operation of the circuit is explained, and after that detailed procedure of design is mentioned.

The operation of this circuit can be divided into two major timing intervals. **A. When the switch**

Figure 1. Simplified topology of Quasi-Resonance flyback converter

is on - The magnetizing inductance L_m of the transformer starts storing energy (As show in Fig. 2a), and the current through L_m , L_r and the switch increases linearly as the voltage across L_m and L_r is constant (Source Voltage). **B. When the switch is off** - The energy stored in L_m begins to transfer to L_1 , which is magnetically coupled to L_2 and L_3 (As shown in Fig. 2b). As a result, current flows through L_3 and L_2 towards the load and control circuit, exhibiting a linearly decreasing waveform. Due to resonance between the resonance capacitor C_r , secondary leakage inductance L_{L2} , and the primary winding's leakage inductance (resonance inductance), a resonant oscillation is established.

Figure 2. Current flow paths in different Operating modes of the converter

This superimposes a sinusoidally oscillating current on the linearly decreasing load current. The resulting sinusoidal oscillation enables zero-current switching (ZCS) of the diode in discontinuous conduction mode (DCM). Also, when the switch is on, a resonance is established between the magnetizing inductance L_m and the drain-source capacitance (C_{oss}), and the inter-turn capacitance of the transformer. If this resonating current is large enough compared to the primary switch peak current then this resonance facilitates valley switching (VS) which reduces switching losses and improves efficiency. At the moment the switch is turned off a voltage of V_{DS} ($V_s + nV_o$) will appear across the switch which is high enough to burn out the switch but because of the damped resonance current, the voltage across the switch reduces. The resonant capacitor is placed across the diode to maintain low switching and conduction loss.

Figure 3. Switching Waveforms of drain to source voltage, primary current and secondary current of flyback transformer

Figure 4. Proposed circuit design of the converter

3. DESIGN OF THE CONVERTER

The design procedure of the proposed converter is presented for 85 VAC – 330 VAC, 50Hz input and 12V, 60W output power. A fixed frequency pulse width modulation controller from Texas Instruments is used which has skip-cycle mode for low-standby power and hiccup mode for continuous overload protection. An initial efficiency of 85% and a power factor of 0.9 is assumed for the reference design. An over-loaded power of 70 watt is allowed so the maximum input power becomes 82.35 W.

Table 1: Electrical Design Parameters

Minimum AC Voltage	85 V
Maximum AC Voltage	330 V
Maximum Input Current	0.97 A
Minimum DC Voltage	96 V
Maximum DC Voltage	467 V
Maximum Output Power	70 W
Output Voltage 1	12 V
Output Ripple Voltage 1	2.7 mV
Transformer Peak Current	6.59 A
Maximum Duty Cycle	0.49
Reflected Voltage	95 V

3.1. Input Filter Design

In each fundamental cycle filter capacitor charges and discharges continuously. To maintain the lowest input DC voltage to the flyback transformer the capacitor should be large enough corresponding to the voltage level, especially in over-load conditions. The proposed design will have 250uf of the filter capacitor.

Capacitance required is =

$$\frac{2 \times \text{Total energy required to deliver}}{\text{Peak voltage at minimum AC input voltage}^2 - (\text{Peak voltage at minimum AC input voltage} - \text{Bus capacitor DC ripple voltage})^2} \quad (1)$$

3.2. Flyback Transformer Design

Depending upon the maximum input magnetizing current and amount of energy stored in the core for every switching cycle the volume and cross-section area of flyback transformer core is decided. Depending upon the reflected voltage of the primary winding the maximum duty cycle is decided.

$$\text{Maximum duty cycle} = \frac{\text{Reflected voltage}}{\text{Reflected voltage} - \text{Minimum DC input voltage}} \quad (2)$$

Also because of the high ripple factor of the primary current the saturation of the core is unavoidable unless treated properly. If because of the maximum primary peak current at over-load condition the flux density inside the core increases its rating the primary turns number should be increased.

$$\text{Primary transformer inductance} = \frac{(\text{Minimum DC input voltage} - \text{Maximum duty cycle})^2}{2 \times \text{Maximum input power} \times \text{Switching frequency} \times \text{Current ripple factor}} \quad (3)$$

$$\text{Minimum primary turns required is} = \frac{\text{Primary peak current} \times \text{Primary transformer inductance} \times 1000000}{B_{max} \times A_e} \quad (4)$$

Table 2: Transformer Design Parameters

Core Type	E36/18/11
Core Material	N87
Effective Core Area	120 mm ²
Maximum Flux Density	43 mT
Inductance	46 μH
Primary Turns	60
Primary Copper Wire Size	22 AWG
Number of Primary Copper Wire in Parallel	1
Primary Layers	2
Secondary 1 Turns (NS1)	8
Secondary 1 Copper Wire Size	16 AWG
Number of Secondary 1 Copper Wire in Parallel	2
Secondary 1 Layers	1
Auxiliary Turns	9
Leakage Inductance	2.3 μH

3.3. Switch Design

A super junction MOSFET is used as a switch, to turn on and off the primary winding. It must withstand the peak primary momentary current while efficiently dissipating heat generated during each switching cycle. To enhance thermal performance, a heat sink with thermal pad or direct-bonded copper substrates can be used for better heat dissipation. As discussed above the drain to source capacitance is used to establish the resonance. The IPA80R600P7 is chosen as it has best in class figure of merit $RDS(on) * E_{oss}$ (energy stored in the output capacitance), along with reduced total gate charge(Qg), input capacitance(Ciss), and output capacitance(Coss). These attributes make it highly suitable for high-frequency applications, ensuring efficient switching performance with minimized losses.

3.4. Output Parameters Design

As discussed before the resonating current must be big enough compared to the output current to actually implement the ZCS of the diode. The diode must withstand the PIV when the switch is on. To reduce the switching loss and conduction loss resonance capacitor is used in parallel with a diode.

Table 3: Component Design Parameters

Secondary 1 Output Capacitor	680 μF
Secondary 1 Output Capacitor in Parallel	1 μF
Secondary 1 LC Filter Inductor	2.2 μH
Secondary 1 LC Filter Capacitor	680 μF

3.5. Controller Parameters Design

LM5023 AC-DC quasi-resonant current mode PWM controller IC is used to control and provide protection against different faulty conditions and overload protection. It can be used for a maximum 130 KHz switching frequency. This design is implemented as fixed fixed-frequency quasi-resonant converter. To maintain the ZCS in fixed frequency is very difficult, in this case using a snubber circuit

will be a good choice to maintain the voltage stress below the tolerable range. Which improves efficiency and reduces the chances of failure. This IC also provides critical conduction mode which ensures if all the residual energy in the transformer core reaches to very low value (when the auxiliary winding voltage falls below 0.35 V) before switching, this ensures the VS of the switch.

$$\text{Resonance Frequency} = \frac{1}{2\pi \times \sqrt{Lm \times Coss}} \tag{5}$$

To avoid saturation in the transformer core it has peak current control mode which detects voltage proportional to the primary current. After the voltage across control pin CS reaches 500 mV, the peak current is limited. It also has skip-cycle mode for low-standby power. In nominal operation, the IC operates in peak current control mode but when load decreases and COMP pin voltage drops below 120 mV, skip-cycle mode is triggered until this voltage reaches 155 mV.

It also has overload protection as hiccup mode for continuous overload protection and cycle-by-cycle overcurrent protection. In hiccup mode it monitors the current sense (CS) pin, if the voltage reaches 500 mV and stays there for a prolonged time (For IVSD = 10 μA, Hiccup delay = 12 ms), the controller detects an overload. If the voltage at the CS pin exceeds the 500-mV limit PWM cycle is immediately terminated for each cycle. A 130 ns time delay is given to avoid switching noise and permanent shutdown, and it reduces stress upon components.

4. SIMULATION AND RESULTS

The proposed design is realised and simulated in LTspice software to confirm the theoretical analysis. The open loop waveform of drain to source voltage and primary current is shown below at 80% load employs soft switching and ensure high efficiency and all theoretical analysis is verified with simulated results. This design gives high efficiency even in low load conditions and power factor is also high at full load conditions (0.9). As discussed before because of applying ZCS and VS the losses comes to very low value. Also, it has reduced electromagnetic interference as the total harmonic distortion is less compared to other flyback converters because of fixed frequency operation. Using the resonance capacitor in parallel with diode reduces conduction loss.

Figure 5. Drain to source voltage and primary current simulated result

Table 4: Output data

Load	Secondary diode loss	Transformer copper loss	Current sense resistor loss	MOSFET and controller loss	Efficiency
100%	3.5 W	1.8 W	0.5 W	2.5 W	86.1%

Table 5: Primary current harmonic components

Harmonic Number	Frequency (kHz)	Fourier Component	Normalized Component	Phase (°)	Normalized Phase (°)
1	100	9.677	1	149.91	0
2	200	2.028	0.2096	-23.86	-173.77
3	300	0.9521	0.09839	-169.82	-319.72
4	400	0.3019	0.03119	-98.24	-248.14
5	500	0.3784	0.0391	127.78	-22.12
6	600	0.2993	0.03093	-55	-204.91
7	700	0.126	0.01302	170.15	20.24
8	800	0.1329	0.01374	-105.61	-255.52
9	900	0.117	0.01209	96.46	-53.44
10	1000	0.1321	0.01365	-72.84	-222.75

5. CONCLUSIONS

This paper analyses the behaviour and operation of a single switch Quasi-Resonant Flyback Converter circuit. The topology employs a resonant inductor in primary and resonant capacitor in secondary which introduces ZCS and near soft switching. This approach significantly reduces switching losses and EMI (Web-2), leading to improved efficiency. However, maintaining the simulated results in real world application is much tricky, magnetic shielding must be properly done between high voltage power circuit and low voltage control circuit to get the desired results. The efficiency of the proposed circuit can be further improved by employing minimum voltage point switching logic and high frequency switching without using the controller IC.

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